

Surface viscosity in simple liquids

Supporting data

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Introduction

The main idea is to speed up the calculation of the zeroes of the function $D(q, \omega)$ (Eq. 1 in the article) by using a polynomial function that has a superset of its solutions. In this notebook we show the full derivation of the dispersion curves, including the analysis of branch cuts.

We start with the necessary imports and some definitions

```
import numpy as np
from sympy import *
from numpy.polynomial.polynomial import polyroots

from matplotlib import pyplot as plt
from matplotlib import rc
import matplotlib as mpl
from cycler import cycler

# our favourite palette
colors={'Bright Red':'#D50032', 'Blue Celeste':'#A4DBE8', 'Yellow':'#F6BE00',
        'Mid Purple':'#500778', 'Bright Green':'#B5BD00', 'Orange':'#EA7600',
        'IOE Blue':'#3255A4', 'Grey':'#8C8279', 'Bright Pink':'#AC145A',
        'Bright Blue':'#0097A9', 'Mid Green':'#8F993E', 'Dark Green':'#555025',
        'Dark Red':'#651D32', 'Dark Purple':'#4B384C', 'Dark Blue':'#003D4C',
        'Dark Brown':'#4E3629', 'Mid Red':'#93272C', 'Mid Blue':'#002855', 'Light
Green':'#BBC592',
        'Light Purple':'#C6B0BC', 'Light Blue':'#8DB9CA',
        'Stone':'#D6D2C4', 'Black':'#000000',}
mpl.rcParams["axes.prop_cycle"]=cycler('color', [c for c in colors.values() if
'000000' not in c])
rc('text', usetex=False)
mpl.rcParams['figure.dpi']=120
```

First, we define some support quantities

```
q, mu, nu, gamma, c, rho = symbols('q mu nu gamma c rho', positive=True)
omega = symbols('omega')

A=4*nu**2*q**4 - 4*I*omega*nu*q**2-omega**2
B=c**2-I*omega*(mu+4*nu/3)
C=-gamma*q**2/rho
D=4*nu**2*q**2
E=q**2-I*omega/nu
```

```
qp=sqrt(q**2-omega**2/B)
qv=sqrt(q**2-I*omega/nu)
```

The dispersion relation (viscous, compressible, non-conducting) is

```
d=-A + sqrt(-omega**2/B+q**2) * (C+D*sqrt(E))
Eq(d,0)
```

$$-4\nu^2q^4 + 4i\nu\omega q^2 + \omega^2 + \sqrt{\frac{\omega^2}{c^2 - i\omega\left(\mu + \frac{4\nu}{3}\right)} + q^2} \left(-\frac{\gamma q^2}{\rho} + 4\nu^2q^2\sqrt{q^2 - \frac{i\omega}{\nu}} \right) = 0$$

We will need the dispersion relation as a numpy function later on. Let's convert it now

```
np_d = lambdify([omega,q,mu,nu,gamma,c,rho], d, "numpy")
```

Now we manipulate the expression to eliminate all square roots (this will add unphysical solutions, to be removed later)

```
Eq(A,sqrt(-omega**2/B+q**2) * (C+D*sqrt(E)))
```

$$4\nu^2q^4 - 4i\nu\omega q^2 - \omega^2 = \sqrt{\frac{\omega^2}{c^2 - i\omega\left(\mu + \frac{4\nu}{3}\right)} + q^2} \left(-\frac{\gamma q^2}{\rho} + 4\nu^2q^2\sqrt{q^2 - \frac{i\omega}{\nu}} \right)$$

```
F=C**2+D**2*E
G=B*q**2-omega**2
```

After some algebra (involving squaring the expression twice) we obtain this polynomial expression:

```
d_poly = ((B*A**2) - G*F)**2 - 4*E*(C*D*G)**2
Eq(((B*A**2) - G*F)**2 , 4*E*(C*D*G)**2)
```

$$\left(\left(c^2 - i\omega\left(\mu + \frac{4\nu}{3}\right) \right) (4\nu^2q^4 - 4i\nu\omega q^2 - \omega^2) - \left(-\omega^2 + q^2\left(c^2 - i\omega\left(\mu + \frac{4\nu}{3}\right) \right) \right) \left(\frac{\gamma^2q^4}{\rho^2} + 16\nu^4q^4\left(q^2 - \frac{i\omega}{\nu} \right) \right) \right)^2 = \frac{16\gamma^2\nu^4q^8 \left(-\omega^2 + q^2\left(c^2 - i\omega\left(\mu + \frac{4\nu}{3}\right) \right) \right)^2 \left(4q^2 - \frac{4i\omega}{\nu} \right)}{\rho^2}$$

The zeroes of $D(q, \omega)$ (i.e. d above) should be the same as those of d_poly (but not vice versa). To be sure that the algebra is correct, we test the polynomial function we just obtained using a random set of parameters

```
from scipy import optimize
# Let's choose a random set of parameters
subs =dict(zip([q,mu, nu, gamma, c, rho],list(np.random.random(6))))
print('the random parameteres:',subs)
# solve with Newton the initial equation starting from the initial guess x0
```

```

test_d = lambdify(omega,      d.evalf(subs=subs) ,modules=["numpy", {'sqrt':
np.sqrt}])
sol = optimize.newton(test_d,x0=1.)
subs['omega'] = sol
print('Check that the polynomial function is also a solution of the correct
dispersion:')
d_poly.evalf(subs=subs) # this should be close enough to zero.

```

the random parameteres: {q: 0.9744362955424901, mu: 0.7389955736624788, nu: 0.6718619408046171, gamma: 0.8593991313385663, c: 0.6708007565179613, rho: 0.8665151524279713}

Check that the polynomial function is also a solution of the correct dispersion:

$$-5.81642737419285 \cdot 10^{-14} - 1.0513861616815 \cdot 10^{-14}i$$

Now we expand the formula into a polynomial of ω

```

poly_omega = expand(d_poly).as_poly(omega)
#poly_omega

```

We then generate a numpy function that returns the coefficients, given the parameters. Note the inverted order to start from the 0th power.

```

coeffs=lambdify([q,mu,nu,gamma,c,rho], poly_omega.all_coeffs()[::-1], 'numpy')
help(coeffs)

```

Help on function _lambdifygenerated:

```
_lambdifygenerated(q, mu, nu, gamma, c, rho)
```

Created with lambdify. Signature:

```
func(q, mu, nu, gamma, c, rho)
```

Expression:

```
[(c**4*gamma**4*q**12 - 64*c**4*gamma**2*nu**4*q**14*rho**2)/rho**4,...
```

Source code:

```

def _lambdifygenerated(q, mu, nu, gamma, c, rho):
    return [(c**4*gamma**4*q**12 - 64*c**4*gamma**2*nu**4*q**14*rho**2)/rho**4,
(1/3)*(288*1j*c**4*gamma**2*nu**3*q**12*rho**2 - 6*1j*c**2*gamma**4*mu*q**12 -
8*1j*c**2*gamma**4*nu*q**12 + 384*1j*c**2*gamma**2*mu*nu**4*q**14*rho**2 +
512*1j*c**2*gamma**2*nu**5*q**14*rho**2)/rho**4,
(1/9)*(432*c**4*gamma**2*nu**2*q**10*rho**2 - 2304*c**4*nu**6*q**12*rho**4 -
18*c**2*gamma**4*q**10 + 1728*c**2*gamma**2*mu*nu**3*q**12*rho**2 +
3168*c**2*gamma**2*nu**4*q**12*rho**2 - 9*gamma**4*mu**2*q**12 -
24*gamma**4*mu*nu*q**12 - 16*gamma**4*nu**2*q**12 +
576*gamma**2*mu**2*nu**4*q**14*rho**2 + 1536*gamma**2*mu*nu**5*q**14*rho**2 +
1024*gamma**2*nu**6*q**14*rho**2)/rho**4, (1/3)*(-48*1j*c**4*gamma**2*nu*q**8*rho**2
+ 2304*1j*c**4*nu**5*q**10*rho**4 - 288*1j*c**2*gamma**2*mu*nu**2*q**10*rho**2 -
768*1j*c**2*gamma**2*nu**3*q**10*rho**2 + 1536*1j*c**2*mu*nu**6*q**12*rho**4 +
512*1j*c**2*nu**7*q**12*rho**4 + 6*1j*gamma**4*mu*q**10 + 8*1j*gamma**4*nu*q**10 -
288*1j*gamma**2*mu**2*nu**3*q**12*rho**2 - 1056*1j*gamma**2*mu*nu**4*q**12*rho**2 -
896*1j*gamma**2*nu**5*q**12*rho**2)/rho**4, (1/9)*(-18*c**4*gamma**2*q**6*rho**2 +
7488*c**4*nu**4*q**8*rho**4 - 288*c**2*gamma**2*mu*nu*q**8*rho**2 -
816*c**2*gamma**2*nu**2*q**8*rho**2 + 13824*c**2*mu*nu**5*q**10*rho**4 +
6912*c**2*nu**6*q**10*rho**4 + 9*gamma**4*q**8 -

```

```

432*gamma**2*mu**2*nu**2*q**10*rho**2 - 2304*gamma**2*mu*nu**3*q**10*rho**2 -
2592*gamma**2*nu**4*q**10*rho**2 + 2304*mu**2*nu**6*q**12*rho**4 +
1536*mu*nu**7*q**12*rho**4 + 256*nu**8*q**12*rho**4)/rho**4,
(1/9)*(-3744*1j*c**4*nu**3*q**6*rho**2 + 36*1j*c**2*gamma**2*mu*q**6 +
192*1j*c**2*gamma**2*nu*q**6 - 14976*1j*c**2*mu*nu**4*q**8*rho**2 -
10752*1j*c**2*nu**5*q**8*rho**2 + 144*1j*gamma**2*mu**2*nu*q**8 +
816*1j*gamma**2*mu*nu**2*q**8 + 1120*1j*gamma**2*nu**3*q**8 -
6912*1j*mu**2*nu**5*q**10*rho**2 - 6912*1j*mu*nu**6*q**10*rho**2 -
1536*1j*nu**7*q**10*rho**2)/rho**2, (1/9)*(-1008*c**4*nu**2*q**4*rho**2 +
18*c**2*gamma**2*q**4 - 7488*c**2*mu*nu**3*q**6*rho**2 - 7392*c**2*nu**4*q**6*rho**2
+ 18*gamma**2*mu**2*q**6 + 192*gamma**2*mu*nu*q**6 + 224*gamma**2*nu**2*q**6 -
7488*mu**2*nu**4*q**8*rho**2 - 10752*mu*nu**5*q**8*rho**2 - 3328*nu**6*q**8*rho**2)/
rho**2, (1/9)*(144*1j*c**4*nu*q**2*rho**2 + 2016*1j*c**2*mu*nu**2*q**4*rho**2 +
2400*1j*c**2*nu**3*q**4*rho**2 - 18*1j*gamma**2*mu*q**4 - 24*1j*gamma**2*nu*q**4 +
3744*1j*mu**2*nu**3*q**6*rho**2 + 7392*1j*mu*nu**4*q**6*rho**2 +
3200*1j*nu**5*q**6*rho**2)/rho**2, c**4 + 32*c**2*mu*nu*q**2 +
(128/3)*c**2*nu**2*q**2 + 112*mu**2*nu**2*q**4 + (800/3)*mu*nu**3*q**4 +
(1408/9)*nu**4*q**4, -2*1j*c**2*mu - 8/3*1j*c**2*nu - 16*1j*mu**2*nu*q**2 -
128/3*1j*mu*nu**2*q**2 - 256/9*1j*nu**3*q**2, -mu**2 - 8/3*mu*nu - 16/9*nu**2]

```

Imported modules:

For example:

```
coeffs(1,1,1,1,1,1)
```

```

[-63.0,
 390j,
 677.0,
 340.66666666666663j,
 2875.4444444444443,
 -4724.8888888888889j,
 -4111.5555555555556,
 2094.8888888888887j,
 610.7777777777778,
 -91.77777777777777j,
 -5.4444444444444445]

```

Selecting the numerical solutions

Now we need a function to go through a branch of a dispersion relation, given an initial seed.

`numpy.polynomial.polynomial.polyroots()` is orders of magnitude faster than general nonlinear solvers. The polynomial that we use has degree 10, so there will be some solutions that will not be also solutions of the original dispersion relation.

```

def near_solution(root,args):
    return root.imag <=0 and np.abs(np_d(*(root,*args))) < 1e-6

```

```

def poly_solve_branches(parms, q_range , dq, q_seed):

```

```

    """
    Finds the solution of a polynomial expression along a branch in a given
    interval,
    starting from a seed.

    Parameters

```

```

-----
parms : array_like
    Input data, five elements in any form that can be converted to a tuple.
    The elements are bulk viscosity, shear viscosity, surface tension,
    speed of sound, density

q_range : array_like
    Two elements denoting the lower and upper limits of the scan along
    the values of q.

dq : float
    interval between sampled values of q. Will be changed to assure an integer
division
    of the interval.

q_seed : float
    Starting point along q for the search of a solution

Returns
-----
out : (2,N) ndarray, with N the number of sampled points along q
"""
from scipy import optimize

mu,nu,gamma,c,rho = parms

# make sure the interval divides in an integer number of bins
N = int((q_range[1]-q_range[0])/dq)
dq = (q_range[1]-q_range[0]) / N

# initial search
args = (q_seed,mu,nu,gamma,c,rho)
tmp = polyroots(coeffs(*args))
#let's eliminate first solutions that are not compatible with the original
dispersion
#(remember that to generate the polynomial we introduced new solutions by
squaring multiple times...)
true_roots = []
for root in tmp:
    if near_solution(root,args):
        # we store everything with positive real and imaginary part
        true_roots.append(root)

# Due to limitations in polyroots(), we remove possible initial solutions
# that are too close to each other.

seed_roots = true_roots

# we will append results along the branch to this list
omegas = [list(seed_roots)]
# and the corresponding values of q
qs = [q_seed]

```

```

# starting from the seed, we go along the two directions
for direction in [1,-1]:
    q = q_seed + direction * dq
    last_roots = seed_roots.copy()
    while q <= q_range[1] and q >= q_range[0]:
        args = (q,mu,nu,gamma,c,rho)
        roots = []
        tmp = polyroots(coeffs(*args))
        for root in tmp:
            if near_solution(root,args):
                roots.append(root)
        roots=np.asarray(roots)

        # now that we have the roots at q, we need to find the
        # closest one to the previous point.
        sorted_roots = []
        for last_root in last_roots:
            if(np.isnan(last_root)):
                sorted_roots.append(np.nan+0*1j)
            else:
                dists = np.abs(roots-last_root)
                if(np.min(dists)>dq*100):
                    sorted_roots.append(np.nan*(1.+1j))
                else:
                    sorted_roots.append(roots[np.argmin(dists)])

        # time to append them to our output
        omegas.append(list(sorted_roots))
        qs.append(q)

        # update last_roots, to be checked at the next iteration
        last_roots = sorted_roots.copy()
        q= q + direction * dq

omegas,qs = np.asarray(omegas), np.asarray(qs)

# As a last step, we sort everything along the q axis.
sort = np.argsort(qs)
qs,omegas = qs[sort], omegas[sort]

return omegas,qs

```

We need now a function that scans the solution space starting from different seeds

```

def poly_solve_branches_multiseed(parms,q_range,dq,seeds):

total_omegas = []
for seed in seeds:
    omegas,qs=poly_solve_branches(parms,q_range,dq,seed)
    # quick workaround some issues in the spanned points
    if qs[0]<0.5*dq:
        omegas=omegas[1:,:]
        qs=qs[1:]

```

```

if len(total_omegas) > 0:
    total_omegas=np.append(total_omegas,omegas, axis=1)
else:
    total_omegas = omegas.copy()

# squash to zero numerical noise for log plots
cond = np.abs(total_omegas.real)<1e-10
total_omegas[cond]= 1j*total_omegas[cond].imag
cond = np.abs(total_omegas.imag)<1e-10
total_omegas[cond]= 1j*total_omegas[cond].real
return total_omegas,qs

```

These are the actual parameters for Lennard-Jones Argon at T=93 K

```

mu,nu,gamma,c,rho = 0.903, 3.1018, 0.977, 5.0, 0.805
parms = mu,nu,gamma,c,rho

```

Let's find the solutions

```

w,q = poly_solve_branches_multiseed(parms, [0,10.], 0.005, [0.1,1.5])

```

We have now to select out duplicated or uninteresting branches by hand. Change the value of n below and see what needs to be kept. There might be a way to automate this, but doing it by hand does not take too much time.

```

def screening(n):
    plt.title('real part')
    plt.plot(q,np.abs(w[:,n].real),'o',c='k',label='singled-out branch')
    plt.semilogy(q,np.abs(w.real),'-',label='x')
    plt.legend()
    plt.show()

    plt.title('imaginary part')
    plt.plot(q,np.abs(w[:,n].imag),'o',c='k',label='singled-out branch')
    plt.semilogy(q,np.abs(w[:,:].imag),'-',label='x')
    plt.legend()
    plt.show()

screening(6)

```


There is a branch that seems to start from nowhere. We need to investigate a bit more in detail. Let's check how the function behaves in the complex plane next to that endpoint

```
# this is the first point where the imaginary part of omega jumps away from zero
column=2
index = np.argwhere(np.abs(w[:,column].imag)>0)[0]
print('q=',q[index],'omega=',w[index,column],'D(q,omega)=' ,np_d(w[index,column],*(q[
index],*parms)))
```

```
q= [0.875] omega= [-4.60768347-3.07569529j] D(q,omega)=
[9.64561764e-12+5.78381787e-12j]
```

```
# We define a function to plot the contour lines of D(q,omega) close to the solution
under scrutiny
```

```
def plot_complex_plate(q,w,parms,range=1.0):
    import matplotlib.cm as cm
```

```

import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

Dw = (1+1j)*range           # range of frequencies
dw = (1. + 1.j)*1e-2 * range # frequency intervals

re = np.arange(w.real-Dw.real, w.real+Dw.real, dw.real)
im = np.arange(w.imag-Dw.imag, w.imag+Dw.imag, dw.imag)
Re, Im = np.meshgrid(re, im)
Z = np_d(Re+1j*Im, *(q, *parms))

val = np_d(w, *(q, *parms))

# real part

fig, ax = plt.subplots()
ax.set_title('Re[$D(q, \omega)$]')
CS = ax.contour(Re, Im, Z.real, levels=25)
ax.clabel(CS, inline=True, fontsize=10)
ax.plot([w.real], [w.imag], 'o', label='$D(q, \omega)=$'+str(val), c='k')
ax.set_xlabel('Re[$\omega$]')
ax.set_ylabel('Im[$\omega$]')
ax.legend()
plt.show()

# imaginary part

fig, ax = plt.subplots()
ax.set_title('Im[$D(q, \omega)$]')

CS = ax.contour(Re, Im, Z.imag, levels=25)
ax.clabel(CS, inline=True, fontsize=10)
ax.plot([w.real], [w.imag], 'o', label='$D(q, \omega)=$'+str(val), c='k')
ax.legend()
ax.set_xlabel('Re[$\omega$]')
ax.set_ylabel('Im[$\omega$]')

plt.show()

# modulo

fig, ax = plt.subplots()
ax.set_title('$\|D(q, \omega)\|$')

CS = ax.contour(Re, Im, np.abs(Z), levels=25)
ax.clabel(CS, inline=True, fontsize=10)
ax.plot([w.real], [w.imag], 'o', label='$D(q, \omega)=$'+str(val), c='k')
ax.legend()
ax.set_xlabel('Re[$\omega$]')
ax.set_ylabel('Im[$\omega$]')
plt.show()

plot_complex_plate(q[index], w[index, column], parms, range=1)

```


In fact, the line where $D(q, \omega) = 0$ ends up to in ridge and does not continue. It seems to be a branch cut of $D(q, \omega)$, with no hydrodynamic limit ($(\omega, q) \rightarrow 0$)

We restrict our selection to the branch without the cut:

```
omegas = {} # we store everything in a dictionary, for later use
```

```
omega = w[:, [4, 5]]
omega = np.abs(omega.real) + np.abs(omega.imag)*1j
```

Let's plot real and imaginary part separately, with the same color code for each branch

```
def plot(q, omega, xlim=[0, 10], name=None):
    fig, ax = plt.subplots(2, 1, sharex='col', sharey='row')
    ax[0].semilogy(q, np.abs(omega.real), '-')
    ax[1].semilogy(q, np.abs(omega.imag), '-')
    ax[0].set_ylabel('$\omega \backslash \tau$')
    ax[1].set_ylabel('$\Gamma \backslash \tau$')
    ax[1].set_xlabel('$q \backslash \sigma$')
    plt.xlim(xlim)
    if name is not None:
        plt.savefig(name)
    plt.show()

plot(q, omega)
```


We are not interested in the real part that starts at high values of q . We remove it by hand here

```
omega[q>1,:] = 1j*omega[q>1,:].imag
plot(q,omega,xlim=[0,1])
omegas[1]=omega.copy()
```


Out of curiosity, we check how the dispersion function behaves close to the branching point

```
# this is the last point where the real part of omega is larger than zero
column=0
index = np.argwhere(np.abs(w[:,column].real)>0)[-1]+1
print('q=',q[index],'omega=',w[index,column],'D(q,omega)=' ,np_d(w[index,column],*(q[
index],*parms)))
```

```
q= [0.215] omega= [-0.-0.07564543j] D(q,omega)= [5.27355937e-16+0.j]
```

we want to interpolate between this point and the first one where the real part drops to zero

```
_q , _w = np.mean([q[index],q[index+1]]),  
np.mean([w[index,column],w[index+1,column]])
```

```
plot_complex_plate(_q,_w,parms,range=1.0)
```


In the plots above one can clearly see the two degenerate solutions.

We repeat the same procedure for other values of viscosities... The screening part is omitted.

```

# Let's half the viscosities
mu,nu,gamma,c,rho = 0.903/2, 3.1018/2, 0.977, 5.0, 0.805
parms = mu,nu,gamma,c,rho
w,q = poly_solve_branches_multiseed(parms, [0,10.], 0.005, [0.05,2.])

omega = w[:,[3,4]]
omega = np.abs(omega.real) + np.abs(omega.imag)*1j
#again, we remove by hand the unwanted branch for the sake of plotting
omega[q>2,:] = 1j*omega[q>2,:].imag
omegas[2]=omega.copy()

# Next, 4, 16
mu,nu,gamma,c,rho = 0.903/4, 3.1018/4, 0.977, 5.0, 0.805
parms = mu,nu,gamma,c,rho
w,q = poly_solve_branches_multiseed(parms, [0,10.], 0.005, [0.05,5.])

omega = w[:,[3,4]]
omega = np.abs(omega.real) + np.abs(omega.imag)*1j
omega[q>4,:] = 1j*omega[q>4,:].imag
omegas[4]=omega.copy()

mu,nu,gamma,c,rho = 0.903/16, 3.1018/16, 0.977, 5.0, 0.805
parms = mu,nu,gamma,c,rho
w,q = poly_solve_branches_multiseed(parms, [0,10.], 0.005, [0.05,9.])

# this time, in the chosen domain, we're ok with taking only the first branch, as
the branching point is further away
omega = w[:,0]
omega = np.abs(omega.real) + np.abs(omega.imag)*1j
omegas[16]=omega.copy()

```

We now plot everything together:

```

fig, ax = plt.subplots(2, 1, sharex='col', sharey='row')
c = [a['color'] for a in list(mpl.rcParams["axes.prop_cycle"])]
for i,f in enumerate(list(omegas.keys())[::-1]):
    omega = omegas[f]
    ax[0].plot(q,omega.real,'-',c=c[i],lw=2,label='scaling = 1/'+str(f))
    ax[1].plot(q,omega.imag,'-',c=c[i],lw=2)
    ax[0].set_ylabel('$\omega \ \tau$')
    ax[1].set_ylabel('$\Gamma \ \tau$')
    ax[1].set_xlabel('$q \ \sigma$')
    ax[0].set_ylim([0,3])
    ax[1].set_ylim([0,10])
    plt.xlim([0,5])

#avoid duplicated labels
handles, labels = ax[0].get_legend_handles_labels()
by_label = dict(zip(labels, handles))
ax[0].legend(by_label.values(), by_label.keys())
plt.savefig('dispersion_curves_linear_scale.png')
plt.show()

```

Linear scale

double logarithmic

semilogarithmic

